

Training Manual 6

Characterization of common Aquaculture Systems in East Africa

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Introduction

Aquaculture in East Africa has grown in importance as fish becomes an increasingly vital part of the regional diet and as natural freshwater sources continue to decline. To meet the rising demand, farmers have adopted a diversity of aquaculture systems suited to different environments and resources. These range from traditional pond systems to more modern approaches such as cage culture in lakes, tank-based systems, and integrated farming that combines fish with crops or livestock. The variety of systems reflects both the need to secure fish as a reliable source of protein and income, and the recognition that controlled production is essential in the face of dwindling capture fisheries and limited freshwater availability.

At the end of this module, the men and women participants will,

- Identify and describe the main aquaculture systems practiced in East Africa.
- Analyze the advantages, disadvantages, and major fish species cultivated in each of each system for sustainable fish farming.
- Describe the factors that influence the choice of aquaculture systems.

Module Timing, Location, and Materials required

No	Session	Estimated time	Location
1.	Identify and describe the main aquaculture systems	4 hrs	Fish Communities
2.	Basic Features, Advantages and Disadvantages of the different aquaculture systems	2hrs	Kajjansi, Living Lab 2
3.	Appropriate fish species for the different Aquaculture Systems	2hrs	Kajjansi, Living Lab 2
Flip charts, manila papers, markers, pens, pencils,			

Session 1: Major Aquaculture Systems in Uganda

Interactive Activity 1: Farm Tours

Divide the participants into three groups and each group will be assigned to take a tour on one of the system. Tell each group to select a team leader and a rapporteur. At each of the station, there will a guide to do the guided tour Divide the participants into three groups and assign each group to visit one of the aquaculture systems (earthen pond, recirculating aquaculture system (RAS), or cage system). Each group should select a team leader to coordinate the activity and a rapporteur to record key observations. At each station, a guide will conduct the tour and explain how the system operates, while the group uses the prepared guiding questions below to make observations, document finding and share a plenary session

- What type of aquaculture system is this (earthen pond, RAS, or cage) and how does it work?
- Where does the water come from, and how is it managed (flow, reuse, or exchange)?
- Which fish species are stocked, and where do the fingerlings come from? How the fish are fed (type of feed, feeding method, frequency)?
- What signs show that the fish are healthy or unhealthy? What practices are used to keep the system clean and safe for the fish? How does the farmer harvest the fish and sell them (local markets, traders, or bigger buyers)?
- What challenges does the farmer face in this system (e.g., water, feed, diseases, predators, costs)?
- Which practices from this farm could be applied on your own farm?

Session 2: Features of Earthened Pond Aquaculture Systems

Interactive Activity 2: Group Presentation

The group provides an overview of the earthen pond system, describing the pond layout, water sources, and basic harvesting method. The team highlights the advantages and disadvantages of the system and explains how it can be integrated with other farm activities. After the presentation, the group opens the floor for the audience to ask questions and seek clarifications on certain issues.

Facilitator's Notes

Earthen pond systems are the most traditional and widespread form of aquaculture practiced in Central Uganda. They are constructed by excavating soil to create large depressions designed to hold water, providing a semi-natural environment to real fish as indicated in figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Types of Earthened Ponds

These ponds usually rely on natural water sources, including springs, perennial streams, or rainfall, which are managed through a system of inlet and outlet pipes, most commonly made of PVC. A defining feature of these ponds is the inclusion of turn-down outlet pipes, drainage channels, and spillways that play a critical role in water management. This infrastructure allows farmers to regulate water levels, carry out partial water exchanges to improve water quality, manage overflow during heavy rainfall, and fully drain the ponds when harvesting fish, typically using nets. By closely mimicking natural ecosystems while still allowing for human control, earthen pond systems provide a relatively low-cost and accessible method of fish farming that fits within the agricultural landscape of the region. These systems are widely used to integrated other services to complement fish rearing as indicated in figure 2.

Figure 2: Integration of Earthen Pond System with Crop and Livestock Enterprises

Advantages and Disadvantages of Earthen Pond Systems

Advantages

- One of the most significant benefits of earthen ponds is their ability to function within a wider farming system. Nutrient-rich pond water, which accumulates waste and organic matter from fish, can be diverted to irrigate crops such as bananas, vegetables, or yams. This not only improves soil fertility but also reduces dependence on expensive chemical fertilizers.
- Livestock waste, particularly from poultry and pigs, can be repurposed as feed for the fish, either directly or by being incorporated into homemade feed formulations. This creates a cycle where waste from one enterprise supports another, improving overall farm efficiency.
- By combining aquaculture with crop and livestock farming, these ponds create a closed-loop system that maximizes resource use. Farmers can produce fish, crops, and livestock in a mutually supportive way, which not only reduces waste but also enhances food security and income diversification. This integrated approach makes farming more sustainable in the long run and reduces vulnerability to market or environmental shocks.
- Compared to more modern systems like tanks or cages, earthen ponds require less capital investment to establish, making them accessible to a wider range of farmers, including smallholders.

Disadvantages

- Earthen ponds are highly susceptible to damage from heavy rainfall and flooding, especially if constructed on sloped or upland terrain. Flood events can breach pond walls, cause water to overflow, and result in mass fish escapes, leading to devastating financial losses for farmers.
- These systems require a relatively large land area, making them less suitable for farmers with limited space. They also consume significant amounts of water, which is a challenge in regions with seasonal droughts or water scarcity. Evaporation and seepage into the soil further increase water loss, reducing efficiency.

- Maintaining suitable water conditions for fish is an ongoing difficulty. Pond water is often used for multiple purposes, such as irrigation, sanitation, or even livestock watering, which can compromise water quality for aquaculture. Without careful monitoring, poor water quality can stress fish, lower growth rates, and increase mortality.
- Because the ponds are open systems, they expose fish to natural predators such as birds, snakes, and other animals. Farmers must constantly remain vigilant or install deterrents, which can add to labor costs. Open ponds also provide less control over breeding and disease management compared to closed systems like tanks or cages, making fish stocks more vulnerable
- Unlike intensive aquaculture systems, earthen ponds offer less precision in controlling key production factors such as water temperature, oxygen levels, and stocking densities. This can limit productivity and make yields less predictable.

Session 3: Basic Characteristics of Recirculating Aquaculture Systems

Interactive Activity 3: Guided Tour

With technical assistance, take a guided tour through the recirculating aquaculture system in Living Lab 2 (Kajjansi). As we move around, carefully observe and note specific aspects of the system.

- Water Inlet and Filtration Units:
- Fish Tanks
- Aeration and Oxygen Supply
- Water Recirculation System
- Monitoring and Control Units

Facilitator Notes:

A Recirculating Aquaculture System (RAS) is a modern fish farming method that allows farmers to rear fish using the same water many times instead of frequently replacing it. The system works by moving water in a cycle where it is cleaned and reused. Fish are kept in tanks where they eat and grow, but at the same time release waste, and some feed remains uneaten. This dirty water leaves the tank and passes through a mechanical filter made of gravel, charcoal, nets, or screens, which trap solid waste such as fish droppings and leftover feed. After this stage, the water goes through a biological filter where good bacteria live and grow. These bacteria play an important role by converting harmful fish waste such as ammonia into safer forms like nitrates, keeping the water healthy for fish survival. The cleaned water then flows into a sump or small collection tank, where it is pumped back to the fish tanks. At this stage, oxygen is also added through aeration or oxygen pumps so that fish have enough air to breathe. Figure 4 below show how this system can be integrated with crops.

Figure 4: Integration of Crops in Recirculating Aquaponic Systems

The system demonstrates an integration between fish farming and crop production through water and nutrient recycling. Fish release waste into the water, which becomes nutrient-rich and is channeled from the fish tank to the crop beds. The plants, such as strawberries and those in the gravel media, use these nutrients as fertilizer, promoting healthy growth. At the same time, the plants act as natural biofilters by purifying the water before it is returned to the reservoir and pumped back into the fish tanks. This integration ensures that nothing goes to waste, as fish support crop production while crops improve water quality for the fish, creating a sustainable closed-loop system.

Advantages and Disadvantages of Recirculating Aquaculture Systems

Advantages

- Recirculating Aquaculture Systems recycle 80–90% of the water, drastically reducing the need for frequent refilling. This makes them especially valuable in water-scarce areas, while also promoting sustainable and responsible resource management.

- Farmers can grow both fish and vegetables at the same time. This integration not only ensures household food security by providing protein and plant-based foods, but it also allows farmers to generate additional income through the sale of surplus produce.
- The nutrient-rich water from fish tanks serves as a natural fertilizer for crops, reducing dependence on chemical inputs. This lowers fertilizer costs while also improving soil health and producing more nutritious, chemical-free vegetables.
- RAS relies on continuous recycling and irrigation, farming is not dependent on rainfall or seasonal changes. Farmers can maintain steady production throughout the year, ensuring consistent food availability and building resilience against climate variability.
- Families gain access to a balanced diet that includes protein from fish and vegetables for essential vitamins and minerals. At the same time, the sale of surplus fish and crops boosts household income, improving overall living standards.

Disadvantages

- Establishing tanks, pumps, aerators, and filtration systems requires significant financial investment, which can be prohibitive for smallholder farmers unless external financial support, subsidies, or loans are available.
- RAS relies heavily on pumps and aerators, which require a constant supply of electricity. Power failures can lead to oxygen depletion within a short time, resulting in fish deaths and significant losses. Energy costs also add to the operational burden in areas with high electricity prices.
- Farmers also need strong technical knowledge to run the system effectively. Constant monitoring of oxygen levels, pH, ammonia, and water temperature is required. Without training and regular supervision, water quality issues can quickly arise, leading to system failure and stock losses.
- Because the water is continuously reused, problems such as pump breakdowns, poor filtration, or contamination can spread rapidly throughout the system. Disease outbreaks are particularly dangerous, as they can affect all the fish and even impact crops at once, causing significant losses.

Session 3: An overview of Cage Aquaculture Systems

Interactive Activity 4: Peer to Peer Interactive Activity

- Pin up pictures of a cage aquaculture system. Ask the participants to:
 - observe the images
 - identify the key components of the cage system.
 - compare the cage system to other aquaculture methods

Share the observation and responses in a plenary

Cages are floating structures with water bodies that allow fish to grow in their natural habitat. Cage aquaculture systems are enclosures placed in lakes, rivers, or reservoirs that allow farmers to grow fish while making use of the natural water flow. They are made up of a floating frame, nets, and a mooring system to keep the cage in place. The free exchange of water brings oxygen and flushes out waste, while the nets protect the fish from predators and keep them contained. For smallholder farmers, floating cages are the most common type because they are relatively simple, low-cost, and well suited to calm inland waters. Figure 5 shows the different types of cage systems.

Figure 5: Different Types of Cage Systems

For good results, farmers should choose sites with sufficient depth, good water circulation, and protection from strong winds. Stocking healthy fingerlings, maintaining appropriate stocking densities, and using quality feed will ensure faster growth and higher survival rates. Farmers also need to monitor fish health, control feeding to avoid waste, and observe simple environmental practices so that water quality remains good for both the farmed fish and surrounding communities.

Advantages

- Cages allow farmers to grow fish in open water bodies such as rivers, lakes, or reservoirs without needing to construct ponds, maximizing the use of available water resources.
- Fish can be stocked at higher densities compared to earthen ponds, which often leads to higher yields and increased income per unit area of water.
- The confined space of cages makes it easier to monitor fish health, feed consumption, and growth rates, as well as to harvest fish when they reach market size.
- Cages can be installed in various suitable water bodies and expanded by adding more units, allowing farmers to scale production with relatively low initial investment.
- Unlike pond systems, cage culture does not require clearing or constructing large land-based ponds, which is particularly beneficial in areas where land is limited or expensive.

Disadvantages

- **Water Quality Dependency:** Since cages are directly in natural water bodies, water quality is largely uncontrollable. Pollution, low oxygen levels, or temperature fluctuations can severely affect fish health.
- Damaged nets or strong currents can allow fish to escape, potentially causing economic loss and ecological issues if non-native species are used.

- Fish in cages are in close proximity to one another, and being in open water makes them susceptible to diseases or parasites from wild fish, requiring careful management.
- Uneaten feed and fish waste are released directly into the water, potentially leading to environmental degradation and water pollution downstream.
- Cages are exposed and may be damaged by storms, strong currents, or human interference, leading to potential losses if not properly secured.

Session 4: Common Fish Species in Aquaculture Systems

Interactive Activity 5: Individual Reflection Exercise

Think about the tour that we had on the first day of the course, what are the common fish species that you saw in the different aquaculture system. Using flash cards, ask the participants to write the name of the fish species that they observed. One fish species per card. In a plenary, let the facilitator cluster the different fish species on the wall.

Pin different pictures of the different fish species and point out the differences between the different fish species

Facilitator Notes:

Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*)

This is the most widely cultured tilapia species in Uganda due to its fast growth, adaptability, and high market demand. It reaches market size of 0.5-1.0 kg per fish in about 6 to 9 months, with good management and feeding practices. Nile tilapia is omnivorous, able to consume both commercial pellets and natural pond productivity, and reproduces rapidly, supporting sustainable stocking in ponds, cages, or recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS). Its high adaptability makes it suitable for all three systems:

Victoria tilapia (*Oreochromis variabilis*)

This is a native fish to Lake Victoria and is adapted to local aquatic environments. It has a moderate growth rate that attains market size in 0.4–0.8 kg per fish in about 9 to 12 months. Victoria tilapia has a mouth brooder and is primarily herbivorous which slows reproduction in confined systems. This species is best suited to earthen ponds and cage aquaculture systems.

Singida tilapia (*Oreochromis esculentus*)

This fish moderately and attains a market size in 0.3–0.7 kg per fish in about 10 to 14 months, and is herbivorous, able to survive largely on natural feeds. Like Victoria tilapia, it is a mouthbrooder with limits its rapid reproduction in enclosed systems.

Singida tilapia is well-suited to earthen ponds and small-scale cages.

African Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*)

This fish is a hardy and widely cultured for its ability to tolerate low oxygen levels and varying water conditions. It is an omnivorous species, feeding on natural pond productivity as well as formulated feeds, making it flexible for different farming systems. African catfish grows relatively fast, reaching market size in 6 to 8 months, typically around 0.7–1.2 kg per fish depending on stocking density and feeding. It can survive in both ponds and cages and is also suitable for RAS due to its hardiness and tolerance to high stocking densities.

Common Carp (*Cyprinus carpio*)

This is a bottom-feeding species that has a moderate growth rate and attains market size in 8 to 12 months, usually around 0.8–1.5 kg per fish depending on pond management and feeding. Common carp is well-suited for earthen ponds due to its feeding behavior and habitat preference, and it can also be grown in cages.

Considerations for Selecting an Aquaculture System

1. **Water Availability and Quality:** Assess the type, quantity, and reliability of water sources. Consider water parameters such as temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, turbidity, and pollution levels. High water quality is critical for fish health and growth, and different systems (cages, ponds, RAS) have varying tolerance and requirements.
2. **Species Selection:** Choose fish species that are well-suited to the chosen system, local climate, and market demand. Some species thrive in cages or ponds, while others require controlled conditions in RAS. Consider growth rate, feed conversion efficiency, disease resistance, and market preferences.
3. **Land and Space Requirements:** Evaluate the land availability and topography. Earthen ponds require significant land and proper soil, cages need sufficient water body area, and RAS requires less land but more infrastructure. The choice should align with the resources you have.
4. **Capital and Operational Costs:** Consider the initial investment for construction, equipment, and stocking, as well as recurring operational costs like feed, energy, labor, and maintenance. RAS has high capital and operational costs, while ponds and cages generally require lower upfront investment.
5. **Management Skills and Labor:** Assess the level of technical knowledge and labor availability. Intensive systems like RAS demand skilled management and constant monitoring, whereas cages and earthen ponds may require moderate skills but still need routine feeding, water quality checks, and disease management.
6. **Environmental and Regulatory Considerations:** Consider environmental impact, local regulations, and sustainability. Some systems may discharge waste into natural water bodies (cages, ponds), requiring mitigation strategies, while others like RAS can recycle water and reduce environmental impact. Also, check permits, zoning, and local guidelines for aquaculture operations.

Summary

Aquaculture in East Africa has become increasingly important due to the growing demand for fish and the decline in capture fisheries. Different systems are adopted depending on local resources, environmental conditions, and farmer objectives. Earthen pond systems are traditional and widely used, relying on soil excavation and natural water sources. They are cost-effective and can be integrated with crop and livestock farming, but they face challenges such as flooding, predators, and less control over water quality. Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS) represent a modern and intensive approach, recycling 80–90% of water and integrating fish with crops in a closed-loop system. While efficient and sustainable, they require high capital investment, technical knowledge, and reliable electricity. Cage systems, on the other hand, utilize open water bodies like lakes and rivers, allowing higher stocking densities and easier monitoring. However, they expose fish to environmental risks, predators, and disease transmission. Across all systems, considerations for selecting an appropriate aquaculture method include water quality, species suitability, land and space availability, cost, technical skills, and environmental sustainability. Integrating aquaculture into broader farming practices enhances food security, income, and resilience for farmers in the region.

Module Key Messages

- Farmers should adopt systems that match their resources, whether low-cost earthen ponds, modern RAS, or cage culture, to maximize sustainability and profitability.
- Combining aquaculture with crop and livestock farming enhances food security, reduces waste, and strengthens household income while promoting sustainable farming systems.
- Successful aquaculture systems require careful evaluation of water availability, fish species selection, land, capital, skills, and environmental impacts to ensure long-term viability.

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